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Highly Cited Works on Human Clinical Trials

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Highly Cited Works on Human Clinical Trials

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine landscapes of the most cited publications on Human Clinical Trials. The top 856 most cited publications on Human Clinical Trials were identified from Web of Science database. The 856 most cited papers on Human Clinical Trials were published between 1989 and 2021 with an average Citation per paper is 1065.46 (Citations range: 400–6319) and are included among the 56 most cited papers in in New England Journal of Medicine with 50851 Citations followed by Journal of Clinical Oncology with 43200 Citations, JAMA Journal of the American Medical Association with 28875 Citations, Nature with 26456 and Lancet with 25181 Citations. The most Cited Countries are: USA with 453423 Citations followed by UK with 100930 Citations, Canada with 84220, France with 61930, Germany with 61752 and India ranked 31st Place according to Citations with 4409. The most cited publications on Human Clinical Trials are highly impactful, landmark studies representing Institutions, Countries, Sources and authorship pattern. A clinical trial is a research study in human volunteers to answer specific health questions. Carefully conducted clinical trials are fastest and safest way to find treatment that work in people and way to improve health. These influential publications have immensely inspiration research for invention of Drugs, Vaccines and Medicines.

Keywords: Human Clinical Trials; Highly Cited works; Citations Classics

Introduction

The Scientometric study of the research has become one of the most used techniques to evaluate the research performance of the Individual researchers, Departments, Institutions, Countries, Subject domains and Journals. The purpose of this study was to bring out a Scientometric evaluation of the global research performance on Human Clinical Trials during 1989-2021. A Scientometric study in this area will help the scientists to understand the progress in research and development.

Clinical trials are research studies performed in people that are aimed at evaluating a medical, surgical, or behavioral intervention. They are the primary way that researchers find out if a new treatment, like a new drug or diet or medical device (for example, a pacemaker) is safe and effective in people. Often a clinical trial is used to learn if a new treatment is more effective and/or has less harmful side effects than the standard treatment. Other clinical trials test ways to find a disease early, sometimes before there are symptoms. Still others

test ways to prevent a health problem. A clinical trial may also look at how to make life better for people living with a life-threatening disease or a chronic health problem. Clinical trials sometimes study the role of caregivers or support groups. Before the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approves a clinical trial to begin, scientists perform laboratory tests and studies in animals to test a potential therapy's safety and efficacy. If these studies show favorable results, the FDA gives approval for the intervention to be tested in humans. (NIG 2021).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study was to perform a Scientometric analysis of all Human Clinical Trials research publications in the world. In particular, the study was confined to the following:

- To find out growth of Publications and Citations;
- To identify the country-wise research contribution and international collaboration;
- To find out the highly productive countries
- To find out Single Country and Multiple Country Publications;
- To find out highly cited publications (Citation Classics);
- To find out highly preferred journals;
- To identify the various types of publications;
- to identify the highly productive institutions;
- To identify the most productive authors

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Web of Science database was used for retrieving data on Human Clinical Trials for all years using the search term 'Human Clinical Trials' in the 'topic' field. Records pertaining to Human Clinical Trials were retrieved only from 1989 onwards. A total of 856 publications received 624361 Citations and these publications were transferred to Biblioshiny, VOSviewer, Histcite for analyzed the data as per objectives of the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Geographical wise Citation of Publications

The study found that the 856 publications came from 61 countries. Table 1 illustrates that United States (USA) is the most Cited and productive country with 453423 Citations for 589 Publications. The second highest Citation recorded by UK with 100930 Citations for 130 publications. The third highest citations recorded by Canada with 84220 Citations for 111 Publications followed by Germany with 61752 Citations, France with 61930 Citations, Italy with 49835 and Australia with 49754 Citations. Besides this, USA shared 68.8% (589) Publications followed by UK with 15.2% of Publications, Canada with 13% of Publications and Germany shared 10.7% of Publications. It noted that 16 countries registered more than 10000 Citations, 28 Countries with

registered more than 5000 Citations and 47 countries recorded more than 1000 Citations.

Table: 1 Most Cited Countries

#	Country	Records	Citations	Country	Records	Citations
1	USA	589	453423	Philippines	5	3674
2	UK	130	100930	Portugal	5	3249
3	Canada	111	84220	Hungary	4	3139
4	France	73	61930	Peru	5	3086
5	Germany	92	61752	Singapore	4	3054
6	Italy	63	49835	Czech Republic	5	3024
7	Australia	56	49754	Romania	3	2723
8	Belgium	44	39767	Uganda	2	2674
9	Netherlands	49	38792	Turkey	4	2530
10	Spain	52	35588	New Zealand	3	2253
11	Switzerland	39	27559	Bangladesh	3	2005
12	Japan	28	16769	Estonia	3	1591
13	Finland	18	12037	Colombia	2	1367
14	Sweden	20	11227	Mexico	2	1319
15	Denmark	19	10950	Slovakia	1	1095
16	Brazil	17	10860	Saudi Arabia	2	1079
17	Ireland	13	9599	Egypt	2	959
18	Austria	14	9222	Chile	1	952
19	Greece	12	8930	Malaysia	1	914
20	Poland	15	8930	Pakistan	1	914
21	Taiwan	10	8216	Croatia	2	851
22	Israel	13	7891	Tunisia	1	777
23	South Korea	11	7685	Cote Ivoire	1	657
24	Peoples R China	12	7614	Senegal	1	657
25	Argentina	10	7501	Kenya	1	610
26	South Africa	7	6136	Nigeria	1	590
27	Thailand	8	5951	Vietnam	1	590
28	Norway	7	5576	Latvia	1	463
29	Russia	7	4964	Zambia	1	448
30	India	6	4409	Jamaica	1	404
31	Slovenia	5	4127			

Country wise Collaboration

The highest number of collaboration by USA with Canada (72), UK (72), Germany (64), France (59), Italy (49), Spain (42) followed by UK with France (39), Canada (34), Germany (34) and Italy (31) Publications. The figure shows Corresponding author's Country i.e. Single Vs Multiple Country Publications.

Table: 2 Country wise Collaboration

From	To	Frequency	From	To	Frequency
USA	CANADA	72	UNITED KINGDOM	AUSTRALIA	23
USA	UNITED KINGDOM	72	FRANCE	NETHERLANDS	22
USA	GERMANY	64	ITALY	SPAIN	22
USA	FRANCE	59	CANADA	SPAIN	21
USA	ITALY	49	USA	BRAZIL	21
USA	SPAIN	42	CANADA	BELGIUM	20
UNITED KINGDOM	FRANCE	39	FRANCE	AUSTRALIA	19
USA	AUSTRALIA	37	NETHERLANDS	BELGIUM	19
UNITED KINGDOM	CANADA	34	UNITED KINGDOM	BELGIUM	19
UNITED KINGDOM	GERMANY	34	CANADA	NETHERLANDS	18
FRANCE	ITALY	32	FRANCE	BELGIUM	18
GERMANY	FRANCE	32	GERMANY	AUSTRALIA	18
USA	BELGIUM	32	GERMANY	ITALY	18
UNITED KINGDOM	ITALY	31	AUSTRALIA	SPAIN	17
USA	NETHERLANDS	31	GERMANY	SPAIN	17
CANADA	FRANCE	30	ITALY	AUSTRALIA	17
USA	SWITZERLAND	28	USA	DENMARK	17
UNITED KINGDOM	NETHERLANDS	27	GERMANY	SWITZERLAND	15

FRANCE	SPAIN	26	ITALY	NETHERLANDS	15
GERMANY	BELGIUM	26	USA	JAPAN	15
CANADA	ITALY	25	AUSTRALIA	BELGIUM	14
GERMANY	NETHERLANDS	25	BELGIUM	SPAIN	14
UNITED KINGDOM	SPAIN	25	ITALY	SWITZERLAND	14
GERMANY	CANADA	24	UNITED KINGDOM	DENMARK	13
CANADA	AUSTRALIA	23	UNITED KINGDOM	SWITZERLAND	13

Three Fields Plot: (Countries, Institutions and Authors)

Country	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
usa	606	467347	1558
england	128	103310	605
canada	110	83113	717
germany	100	69949	482
france	85	72743	631
italy	77	59496	443
netherlands	57	44973	292
australia	55	49340	357
spain	54	37981	408
belgium	50	45348	371
switzerland	42	30013	183
japan	28	16769	71
scotland	28	17047	65
denmark	24	15255	108
sweden	23	13451	110
brazil	23	15619	243
finland	17	11381	107
austria	17	12966	113
poland	16	11563	74
israel	16	11902	39

Citation Network of Countries

Citation Network of USA

England - Citation network

Canada - Citation network

Germany - Citation network

Corresponding Author's Country

The highest number of SCP (368) and MCP(151) by USA with 519 publications and MCP Ratio is 0.291 followed by UK with 58 Publications (SCP:32 and MCP:26 and MCP Ratio is 0.448. The MCP ratio ranged from 0.125 to 1.

Table: Corresponding Author's Country

Country	Articles	Frequency	SCP	MCP	MCP_Ratio
USA	519	0.62455	368	151	0.291
UNITED KINGDOM	58	0.0698	32	26	0.448
CANADA	38	0.04573	23	15	0.395
GERMANY	28	0.03369	8	20	0.714
ITALY	26	0.03129	14	12	0.462
AUSTRALIA	16	0.01925	7	9	0.562
FRANCE	16	0.01925	8	8	0.5
NETHERLANDS	16	0.01925	6	10	0.625
SPAIN	15	0.01805	5	10	0.667
BELGIUM	14	0.01685	6	8	0.571
SWITZERLAND	11	0.01324	6	5	0.455
JAPAN	9	0.01083	7	2	0.222
CHINA	8	0.00963	7	1	0.125
FINLAND	8	0.00963	4	4	0.5
DENMARK	7	0.00842	4	3	0.429
SWEDEN	7	0.00842	4	3	0.429
AUSTRIA	4	0.00481	0	4	1
BRAZIL	4	0.00481	1	3	0.75
INDIA	4	0.00481	3	1	0.25
IRELAND	4	0.00481	1	3	0.75
GREECE	3	0.00361	1	2	0.667
POLAND	3	0.00361	3	0	0
PORTUGAL	3	0.00361	1	2	0.667
THAILAND	2	0.00241	0	2	1
ISRAEL	1	0.0012	1	0	0
KOREA	1	0.0012	1	0	0
NEW ZEALAND	1	0.0012	1	0	0
RUSSIA	1	0.0012	0	1	1
SAUDI ARABIA	1	0.0012	0	1	1
SINGAPORE	1	0.0012	1	0	0
SLOVAKIA	1	0.0012	0	1	1
SOUTH AFRICA	1	0.0012	0	1	1

Most Cited and Productive Authors

It was identified that Eight authors(Doherty GM, Haugen BR, Mandel SJ, Pacini F, Schlumberger M, Sherman SI, Steward DL) have registered the highest number of Citations with 9107 for 2 Publications(ACPP-4553.50) followed by Vincent JL with 8918 Citations for 7 Publications (ACPP-1274), Hammer SM with 8816 Citations for 12 Publications (ACPP-734.6), Sandborn W J with 7162 Citations for 10 Publications (ACPP-716.2), Jain RK with 7114 Citations for 2 Publications (ACPP-3557) and Levy MM with 7000 Citations for 7 Publications (ACPP-1750). It is note that 36 Authors registered more than 5000 Citations and 1528 authors recorded more than 1000 Citations. The most productive authors identified are: Hammer SM with 12 Publications (ACPP-734.6), followed by Hirsch MS with 11 Publications(ACPP-605.27), Richman DD with 10 publications(ACPP-599.8), Sandhorn WJ with 10 Publications(ACPP716.2).

Most Cited and Productive Authors

#	Author	Records	Citations	Author	Records	Citations
1	Hammer SM	12	8816	Doherty GM	2	9107
2	Hirsch MS	11	6658	Haugen BR	2	9107
3	Richman DD	10	5998	Mandel SJ	2	9107
4	Sandborn WJ	10	7162	Pacini F	2	9107
5	Jacobsen DM	9	5532	Schlumberger M	2	9107
6	Montaner JSG	8	5148	Sherman SI	2	9107
7	Schooley RT	8	5208	Steward DL	2	9107
8	Fischl MA	7	5975	Tuttle RM	2	9107
9	Katzenstein DA	7	4177	Vincent JL	7	8918
10	Perez EA	7	6911	Hammer SM	12	8816
11	Vella S	7	4095	Sandborn WJ	10	7162
12	Vincent JL	7	8918	Jain RK	2	7114
13	Volberding PA	7	4488	Levy MM	4	7000
14	Abraham E	6	6901	Fischl B	3	6914
15	Baselga J	6	4212	Perez EA	7	6911
16	Hayes DF	6	5952	Abraham E	6	6901

17	Saag MS	6	4282	de Bono JS	3	6843
18	Thompson MA	6	3644	Hirsch MS	11	6658
19	Yeni PG	6	3817	Marshall JC	4	6593
20	Bone RC	5	3645	Carmeliet P	1	6319
21	Carpenter CCJ	5	3051	Aggarwal BB	4	6278
22	Gatell JM	5	3307	Scher HI	4	6241
23	Rutgeerts P	5	3640	Cohen J	3	6169
24	Sosman JA	5	4329	Ramsay G	3	6169
25	Aggarwal BB	4	6278	Sellers WR	4	6035
26	Anderson KC	4	2511	Richman DD	10	5998
27	Balk RA	4	2802	Fischl MA	7	5975
28	Burris HA	4	3022	Hayes DF	6	5952
29	Caplan AI	4	3104	Opal SM	4	5829
30	Colombel JF	4	3145	Fink MP	4	5748

Three Fields Plot: Authors, Sources and institutions

Author	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
hammer, sm	10	7379	349
hirsch, ms	9	5221	312
jacobsen, dm	7	4095	269
richman, dd	8	4561	269
vella, s	7	4095	269
montaner, jsg	6	3711	245
katzenstein, da	7	4177	238
fischl, ma	6	5209	236
schooley, rt	6	3771	223
carpenter, ccj	5	3051	195
saag, ms	6	4282	195
volberding, pa	5	3051	195
yeni, pg	5	3051	195
rutgeerts, paul	5	3640	19
sandborn, william j.	8	5885	19
perez, edith a.	5	5223	0
vincent, jl	5	7598	0

Bibliographic Forms of Publications

A total 856 publications 470 (54.91 %) are articles published in journals. Reviews are 344 (40.2 %), followed by Article; Proceedings Paper 22 (2.6 %), Review; Book Chapter 9 and Editorial Material 9 (3.44 %) respectively. It is note that researchers have preferred 7 bibliographical forms of communications for their research. It is also note that Journal articles and Review are more preferred.

Bibliographical forms of Communications

#	Document Type	Records	%	Citations
1	Article	470	54.91	343204
2	Review	344	40.2	255449
3	Article; Proceedings Paper	22	2.6	14987
4	Review; Book Chapter	9	1.1	4763
5	Editorial Material	9	1.1	4735
6	Article; Retracted Publication	1	0.1	770
7	Note	1	0.1	453

Most Preferred and Highly Cited Sources

In the study, 60 highly Cited and preferred journals publishing Human Clinical Trials research papers were identified and listed in the below table. Table indicated below shows the impact of the most Cited Journals. NEW ENGLAND

JOURNAL OF MEDICINE is the highly Cited journal with 50851 Citations, followed by JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY with 43200 Citations, JAMA-JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION with 28875 Citations, NATURE with 26456 Citations, and LANCET with 25181 Citations.

It was found that NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE has the highest impact factor (74.699) followed by NATURE REVIEWS DRUG DISCOVERY (64.797), LANCET (60.392), NATURE REVIEWS CANCER (53.030), JAMA-JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION (45.540), SCIENCE (41.845), NATURE REVIEWS IMMUNOLOGY (40.358). It is note that 35 Journals registered more than 40 Impact Factor and it shows quality of research in the field of Human Clinical Trials.

Table: Most Preferred and Highly Cited Sources

#	Journal	Impact Factor	Records	Citations
1	NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE	74.699	56	50851
2	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY	32.956	63	43200
3	JAMA-JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION	45.540	44	28875
4	NATURE	26	20	26456
5	LANCET	60.392	30	25181
6	NATURE REVIEWS DRUG DISCOVERY	64.797	18	13875
7	BLOOD	17.794	19	13797
8	COCHRANE DATABASE OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS	7.890	18	13020
9	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	9.412	22	12936
10	CANCER RESEARCH	9.727	20	12764
11	NATURE REVIEWS CANCER	53.030	13	11222
12	SCIENCE	41.845	9	10385
13	THYROID	7.557	3	9625
14	CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE	7.414	6	7958
15	ANNALS OF INTERNAL MEDICINE	21.317	13	7454
16	CIRCULATION	23.603	12	7383
17	GASTROENTEROLOGY	19.809	10	7141
18	CLINICAL CANCER RESEARCH	10.107	10	7094
19	NEUROIMAGE	5.902	3	6914
20	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF CLINICAL NUTRITION	6.766	8	6473
21	NATURE MEDICINE	36.230	11	6371
22	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL INVESTIGATION	11.864	6	5700
23	CLINICAL INFECTIOUS DISEASES	9.117	8	5375
24	ENDOCRINE REVIEWS	15.745	6	5311
25	JNCI-JOURNAL OF THE NATIONAL CANCER INSTITUTE	11.577	6	4913
26	ANNALS OF ONCOLOGY	18.274	5	4820
27	LANCET ONCOLOGY	33.752	7	4746
28	PAIN	6.029	3	4014
29	NATURE REVIEWS IMMUNOLOGY	40.358	6	4013
30	PEDIATRICS	5.417	2	3990
31	SCIENCE TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE	16.304	5	3877
32	PHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEWS	17.814	5	3830
33	STEM CELLS	3.231	5	3601
34	MOLECULAR PHARMACEUTICS	4.57	2	3565
35	FASEB JOURNAL	4.966	1	3359

36	ANTICANCER RESEARCH	1.937	2	3332
37	JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN COLLEGE OF CARDIOLOGY	20.589	5	3308
38	JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL CHEMISTRY	4.238	4	2586
39	ONCOGENE	7.971	4	2521
40	ARTHRITIS AND RHEUMATISM	4.7	4	2520
41	PHARMACOLOGY & THERAPEUTICS	11.127	4	2473
42	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF TRANSPLANTATION	7.163	3	2409
43	ANNUAL REVIEW OF IMMUNOLOGY	19.900	3	2358
44	BRAIN	11.337	4	2357
45	JOURNAL OF CONTROLLED RELEASE	7.633	3	2350
46	LANCET NEUROLOGY	30.039	4	2333
47	CLINICAL NEUROPHYSIOLOGY	3.614	3	2331
48	CLINICAL MICROBIOLOGY REVIEWS	17.406	4	2317
49	GUT	19.819	4	2234
50	ANNUAL REVIEW OF MEDICINE	9.716	3	2218
51	DIABETES CARE	15.3	5	2210
52	NATURE GENETICS	27.603	2	2181
53	LANCET INFECTIOUS DISEASES	36.421	2	2153
54	ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS AND CHEMOTHERAPY	4.715	2	2048
55	BRITISH JOURNAL OF CANCER	5.791	4	2040
56	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR BIOCHEMISTRY	2.057	2	1962
57	NATURE BIOTECHNOLOGY	36.558	3	1961
58	CHEST	9.657	3	1953
59	HUMAN REPRODUCTION UPDATE	12.684	2	1943
60	NATURE REVIEWS GENETICS	33.133	4	1859

Activate Windows

Three Fields Plot: (Sources, Institutions and Authors)

Source	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
new england journal of medicine	56	50851	53
jama-journal of the american medi...	44	28875	40
journal of clinical oncology	63	43200	39
lancet	30	25181	26
gastroenterology	10	7141	16
annals of internal medicine	13	7454	12
blood	19	13797	12
cancer research	20	12764	11
clinical cancer research	10	7094	11
journal of clinical investigation	6	5700	10
nature reviews drug discovery	18	13875	10
proceedings of the national acade...	22	12936	9
critical care medicine	6	7958	7
endocrine reviews	6	5311	6
lancet oncology	7	4746	6
science	9	10385	6
cochrane database of systematic r...	18	13020	5
nature	20	26456	5
nature medicine	11	6371	5
annals of oncology	5	4820	4

Most Productive year

This table gives the year wise distribution of articles. Out of total 856 articles, the maximum numbers of articles are in the year 2005 contributing 61 articles, which is 41827 to the total Citations. The minimum numbers of articles are in the year of 2019 with 1 (455 Citations), 1990 with 1 (439 Citations), 1989 with 1 (723 Citations) and 1992 with 2 (910 Citations). This table also shows the citation pattern of articles distributed in the year of 2008 with 43606 Citations for 59 Publications followed by 2005 with 41827 Citations for 61 Publications, 2006 with 39638 Citations for 51 articles. It is noted that almost all the year registered highly cited papers.

Table: Most Productive year

#	Citation Impact			Publication Impact		
	Year	Records	Citations	Year	Records	Citations
2	2008	59	43606	2005	61	41827

1	2005	61	41827	2008	59	43606
4	2006	51	39638	2007	47	38741
6	2007	47	38741	2009	44	36922
7	2000	46	38411	2003	54	36542
8	2009	44	36922	2011	42	32232
3	2003	54	36542	2006	51	39638
9	2011	42	32232	2002	47	30069
5	2002	47	30069	2000	46	38411
10	2012	37	29081	2012	37	29081
12	2004	36	27335	2001	36	26737
11	2001	36	26737	2004	36	27335
13	2013	33	22690	2013	33	22690
15	2010	29	21604	1998	27	17770
16	1998	27	17770	1999	25	17233
17	1999	25	17233	2014	30	17191
14	2014	30	17191	2010	29	21604
20	1996	22	14982	1995	23	14875
19	2015	23	14896	2015	23	14896
18	1995	23	14875	1996	22	14982
21	1997	21	14607	1997	21	14607
22	2016	15	13362	2016	15	13362
24	1994	8	8115	1993	10	6637
23	1993	10	6637	1994	8	8115
25	1991	7	5981	1991	7	5981
27	2020	7	4706	2017	7	3832
26	2017	7	3832	2020	7	4706
28	2018	4	2212	2018	4	2212
29	1992	2	910	1992	2	910
30	1989	1	723	1989	1	723
32	2019	1	455	1990	1	439
31	1990	1	439	2019	1	455

Most Cited Institutions

Among all the Institutions, the highly productive Institutions were: Harvard University from USA with 82 publications and received 78100 Citations

followed by University Calif San Francisco - USA with 49 publications and 38573 citations, University Colorado - USA with 31 publications and 36448 citations, Mem Sloan Kettering Cancer Centre- USA with 36 publications and 36300 citations. USA Institutes are dominating in terms of Citation and Publications in the field of Human Clinical Trials research. 46 Institutes were recorded 10000 and above Citations and 694 institutions were registered 1000 and above citations.

Table: Most Cited Institutions

#	Institution	Country	Records	Citations
1	Harvard University	USA	82	78100
2	University Calif San Francisco	USA	49	38573
3	University Colorado	USA	31	36448
4	Mem Sloan Kettering Cancer Centre	USA	36	36300
5	University Texas	USA	35	31511
6	Johns Hopkins University	USA	36	31225
7	University Calif San Diego	USA	35	29371
8	University Texas MD Anderson Cancer Centre	USA	23	28086
9	Massachusetts Gen Hospital	USA	23	27857
10	University Pittsburgh	USA	31	27699
11	University Washington	USA	31	25858
12	Dana Farber Cancer Institute	USA	30	25265
13	Duke University	USA	29	24722
14	University Penn	USA	20	23929
15	Mayo Clinic	USA	24	23299
16	University Calif Los Angeles	USA	27	23184
17	Stanford University	USA	32	21995
18	University Toronto	Canada	24	19786
19	University N Carolina	USA	29	18864
20	Institute Gustave Roussy	France	12	18427
21	University Cincinnati	USA	11	17886
22	University of Michigan	USA	22	16672
23	NIAID	USA	17	16608
24	Boston University	USA	11	15673
25	Washington University	USA	22	15529
26	University Miami	USA	18	15271
27	Emory University	USA	22	14287
28	Yale University	USA	20	14232
29	NCI	USA	25	14133
30	Oregon Health & Science University	USA	14	13611
31	University of Chicago	USA	19	13473
32	University British Columbia	Canada	17	13142
33	MIT	USA	10	12892
34	University Oxford	UK	14	12325
35	Columbia University	USA	16	12193
36	University of Minnesota	USA	14	12049
37	Brigham & Women's Hospital	USA	17	12010
38	Vanderbilt University	USA	11	11888
39	Tufts University	USA	12	11772
40	Indiana University	USA	16	11503
41	Brown University	USA	13	11049

42	University of Rochester	USA	13	10882
43	Northwestern University	USA	16	10854
44	Genentech Inc	USA	11	10533
45	University Siena	Italy	4	10471
46	Howard Hughes Med Institute	USA	4	10447

Three Fields plot: Affiliations, Authors and Institutions

Organization	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
harvard univ	81	77100	886
univ calif san diego	35	29371	682
univ calif san francisco	47	35873	590
univ colorado	30	34748	543
univ miami	16	13576	492
stanford univ	30	20307	446
hop bichat claude bernard	8	4890	435
ist super sanita	8	4803	432
univ british columbia	16	12142	408
vet affairs med ctr	11	7918	398
int aids soc usa	7	4441	381
brown univ	12	10260	367
aids res consortium atlanta	6	3846	340
niaid	17	16608	304
univ alabama birmingham	15	9066	299
univ rochester	13	10882	298
univ alabama	8	6555	273
univ barcelona	11	8059	271
univ n carolina	26	16702	267
northwestern univ	14	9598	252

Highly Cited Works

856 papers have received more than 400 citations and it has considered as Citation Classic Paper (In general, a publication cited more than 400 times should be considered a classic; but in some fields with fewer researchers, 100 citations might qualify a work- **Eugene Garfield**), besides this the citations count has been taken as the number of citations received by each paper since these were published till March 2021. Table presents the pattern of frequently cited papers. It is found that there were 123 papers, which have received more than 1000 citations. The most cited paper “Carmeliet P, Jain RK, (2000, Canada). Angiogenesis in cancer and other diseases”, published in NATURE with 6319 Citations followed by Desikan RS, Segonne F, Fischl B, Quinn BT, Dickerson BC, et al. (2006, Slovakia, England and USA). “An automated labeling system for subdividing the human cerebral cortex on MRI scans into gyral based regions of interest”, published in NEUROIMAGE with 4933 citations. Top 20 journals are indexed during 2000 to 2016.

Table: Highly Cited Works

#	Date / Author / Journal	LCS	GCS	LCR	CR
1	186 Carmeliet P, Jain RK, Angiogenesis in cancer and other diseases NATURE. 2000 SEP 14; 407 (6801): 249-257	3	6319	1	75
2	460 Desikan RS, Segonne F, Fischl B, Quinn BT, Dickerson BC, et al., An automated labeling system for subdividing the human cerebral cortex on MRI scans into gyral based regions of interest, NEUROIMAGE. 2006 JUL 1; 31 (3): 968-980	1	4933	0	63
3	826 Haugen BR, Alexander EK, Bible KC, Doherty GM, Mandel SJ, et al., 2015 American Thyroid Association Management Guidelines for Adult Patients with Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer The American Thyroid Association Guidelines Task Force on Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer, THYROID. 2016 JAN 1; 26 (1): 1-133	0	4579	1	1071
4	620 Cooper DS, Doherty GM, Haugen BR, Kloos RT, Lee SL, et al. Revised American Thyroid Association Management Guidelines for Patients with Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer THYROID. 2009 NOV; 19 (11): 1167-1214	2	4528	0	435
5	294 Levy MM, Fink MP, Marshall JC, Abraham E, Angus D, et al. 2001 SCCM/ESICM/ACCP/ATS/SIS International Sepsis Definitions Conference CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE. 2003 APR; 31 (4): 1250-1256	2	3636	0	41
6	718 Barretina J, Caponigro G, Stransky N, Venkatesan K, Margolin AA, et al. The Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia enables predictive modelling of anticancer drug sensitivity, NATURE. 2012 MAR 29; 483 (7391): 603-607	0	3492	0	26
7	378 Gartner LM, Morton J, Lawrence RA, Naylor AJ, O'Hare D, et al. Breastfeeding and the use of human milk PEDIATRICS. 2005 FEB; 115 (2): 496-506	0	3475	0	215
8	60 Dinarello CA, Biologic basis for interleukin-1 in disease BLOOD. 1996 MAR 15; 87 (6): 2095-2147	0	3428	3	585
9	541 Reagan-Shaw S, Nihal M, Ahmad N Dose translation from animal to human studies revisited	0	3359	0	20

	FASEB JOURNAL. 2008 MAR; 22 (3): 659-661				
10	228 Farrar JT, Young JP, LaMoreaux L, Werth JL, Poole RM Clinical importance of changes in chronic pain intensity measured on an 11-point numerical pain rating scale, PAIN. 2001 NOV; 94 (2): 149-158	1	2970	0	22
11	518 Anand P, Kunnumakkara AB, Newman RA, Aggarwal BB Bioavailability of curcumin: Problems and promises MOLECULAR PHARMACEUTICS. 2007 NOV-DEC; 4 (6): 807-818	3	2868	4	85
12	29 CONNOR EM, SPERLING RS, GELBER R, KISELEV P, SCOTT G, et al. REDUCTION OF MATERNAL-INFANT TRANSMISSION OF HUMAN-IMMUNODEFICIENCY-VIRUS TYPE-1 WITH ZIDOVUDINE TREATMENT NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE. 1994 NOV 3; 331 (18): 1173-1180	6	2719	0	39
13	681 De Bono JS, Logothetis CJ, Molina A, Fizazi K, North S, et al. Abiraterone and Increased Survival in Metastatic Prostate Cancer NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE. 2011 MAY 26; 364 (21): 1995-2005	0	2705	0	50
14	700 Macdonald G, Higgins JPT, Ramchandani P, Valentine JC, Bronger LP, et al. Cognitive-behavioural interventions for children who have been sexually abused COCHRANE DATABASE OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS. 2012; (5): Art. No. CD001930	0	2659	0	102
15	500 Moore MJ, Goldstein D, Hamm J, Figer A, Hecht JR, et al. Erlotinib plus gemcitabine compared with gemcitabine alone in patients with advanced pancreatic cancer: A phase III trial of the National Cancer Institute of Canada clinical trials group JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY. 2007 MAY 20; 25 (15): 1960-1966	3	2633	0	36
16	483 Wolff AC, Hammond MEH, Schwartz JN, Hagerty KL, Allred DC, et al. American Society of Clinical Oncology/College of American Pathologists guideline recommendations for human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 testing in breast cancer, JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY. 2007 JAN 1; 25 (1): 118-145	2	2618	1	88
17	179 Rayman MP, The importance of selenium to human health LANCET. 2000 JUL 15; 356 (9225): 233-241	2	2587	0	85
18	188 Noseworthy JH, Lucchinetti C, Rodriguez M, Weinshenker BG Medical progress: Multiple sclerosis. NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE. 2000 SEP 28; 343 (13): 938-952	0	2527	1	106
19	684 Lehmann BD, Bauer JA, Chen X, Sanders ME, Chakravarthy AB, et al. Identification of human triple-negative breast cancer subtypes and preclinical models for selection of targeted therapies JOURNAL OF CLINICAL INVESTIGATION. 2011 JUL; 121 (7): 2750-2767	0	2513	2	78
20	353 Ferrara N, Vascular endothelial growth factor: Basic science and clinical progress, ENDOCRINE REVIEWS. 2004 AUG; 25 (4): 581-611	2	2442	2	435

Document	Citations	Links
cheng (2001)	1476	12
hammer (1997)	2158	11
sharma (2004)	819	11
sharma (2001)	587	10
aggarwal (2003)	1856	9
colombel (2007)	1425	9
sharma (2005)	1075	9
koc (2000)	810	9
carpenter (1996)	539	9
zhou (2011)	406	9
maini (1999)	1922	8
carpenter (2000)	844	8
carpenter (1998)	642	8
mannon (2004)	623	8
sandborn (2008)	515	8
naksuriya (2014)	475	8
strimpakos (2008)	432	8
singh (2011)	404	8
anand (2007)	2868	7
coussens (2002)	2084	7
davis (2010)	1791	7

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

As per the Web of Science database, a total of 856 publications were published on Human Clinical Trials, which received 624361 citations during 1989-2020. The highest number of citations (43606) were received in 2008. A total of 624361 citations were included in 856 publications with an average of 19511.27 citations per Year in Human Clinical Trials research. USA is identified as the most leading country in terms of publications and Citations with 453423 Citations for 589 Publications in Human Clinical Trials research. It has shared 68.8 percent of world publications. India holds 32nd rank with 6 papers which has 0.7 percent share and 31st rank with received 4409 Citations. The most cited journals are New England Journal of Medicine with 50851 Citations followed by Journal of Clinical Oncology with 43200 Citations, JAMA Journal of the American Medical Association with 28875 Citations, Nature with 26456 and Lancet with 25181 Citations. The most Cited Countries are: USA with 453423 Citations followed by UK with 100930 Citations, Canada with 84220, France with 61930, Germany with 61752 and India ranked 31st Place according to Citations with 4409. The most productive authors identified are: Hammer SM

with 12 Publications (ACPP-734.6), followed by Hirsch MS with 11 Publications (ACPP-605.27), Richman DD with 10 publications (ACPP-599.8), Sandhorn WJ with 10 Publications (ACPP716.2). The most cited paper “Carmeliet P, Jain RK, (2000, Canada). Angiogenesis in cancer and other diseases”, published in NATURE with 6319 Citations followed by Desikan RS, Segonne F, Fischl B, Quinn BT, Dickerson BC, et al. (2006, Slovakia, England and USA). “An automated labeling system for subdividing the human cerebral cortex on MRI scans into gyral based regions of interest”, published in NEUROIMAGE with 4933 citations. Top 20 journals are indexed during 2000 to 2016. The most cited publications on Human Clinical Trials are highly impactful, landmark studies representing Institutions, Countries, Sources and authorship pattern. A clinical trial is a research study in human volunteers to answer specific health questions. Carefully conducted clinical trials are fastest and safest way to find treatment that work in people and way to improve health. These influential publications have immensely inspiration research for invention of Drugs, Vaccines and Medicines

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- **Surulinathi, M., Balasubramani, R., and Amsaveni, N (2020).** COVID-19 research output in 2020: The Global Perspective using Scientometric Study, *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-18.
- **Sebastiyan, R., Babu, V. R., & Surulinathi, M. (2020).** Mapping of research output in food economics: A scientometric analysis. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Summer 9-1-2020, 1-18.
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